

Abstract Details

Title: **Socio-economic and clinical needs and challenges for early detection and progression monitoring of Alzheimer's disease in primary healthcare**

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The introduction of blood-based biomarkers for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) diagnosis has facilitated faster, cost-effective, and less invasive clinical pathways [Hampel et al., 2023]. This advancement ranges from early detection of "at-risk" individuals in primary healthcare settings to monitoring treatment response and disease progression in specialized care. Within the scope of the EU-funded 2D-BioPAD project (GA No. 101120706), the authors investigated the socio-economic and clinical requirements and challenges associated with blood-based (specifically plasma) AD diagnostics, primarily in primary healthcare settings. This exploration followed a three-step patient and public involvement and engagement approach. A knowledge base was created through desk research using relevant literature and input from 2D-BioPAD experts. Subsequently, 26 interviews were conducted with Technology Providers (19%), Healthcare Professionals (HCPs) (35%), Decision/Policy Makers (19%), Patients, and Caregivers (27%), refining the initial findings. Additionally, an online survey garnered 96 responses from Biomarker Experts (13.54%), Decision/Policy Makers (13.54%), Primary and Specialized healthcare professionals (HCPs) (30.21%), Patients (11.46%), and Caregivers (31.25%), enriching the knowledge base with insights from a broader audience. The findings underscored the necessity to: 1. Increase public awareness regarding AD and novel diagnostics; 2. Educate HCPs on biomarker-related clinical protocols, starting with primary HCPs; 3. Develop precise, minimally invasive, cost-effective, and accessible point-of-care (PoC) in-vitro diagnostics (IVD) based on reliable biomarkers for use by Primary HCPs; 4. Offer personalized treatment, effective counseling, and referral, including mental health support; 5. Disclose diagnostics' sensitivity, specificity, and reliability based on solid evidence and benchmarks; 6. Provide clear, easily understandable information covering the testing procedure, biomarkers, and post-results next steps; 7. Standardize processes and costs across Europe, with a focus on improved insurance coverage for diagnostics reimbursement. Addressing these diverse needs and challenges is critical for enhancing the AD diagnostic process, ultimately leading to improved outcomes for patients and caregivers.

